

Reflection/Refraction, Spatial Invariance and Origin of Statistical Nature of Problem

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It is known that if a photon hits a surface with a different index of refraction (at an angle within a certain range), it has a specific probability “a” to reflect and 1-a to refract. In this note we ask: Where does this statistical nature come from?

In previous notes, we have considered Fermat’s principle applied separately to explain two dimensional reflection and refraction. We have also used the idea of a difference of squares and energy conservation in one dimensional reflection/refraction to find values of the probabilities. The question we ask is: Why are there probabilities in the first place? Is there some general idea at work despite the complicated details of the photon interacting with the atoms of the new medium. We argue the general notion is due to the idea of spatial invariance which is linked to the translation operator d/dx which in turn is linked to a p impulse occurring at a given x . Thus the variables p and x are linked through the notion of an impulse existing at some x . The idea that d/dx may operate on a function of constant p and x to yield p , implies the function of p, x should have physical meaning. This is a problem as classically a particle moving with constant p should not be associated with any function of x except a constant. (All x points are the “same”.)

Thus we argue that a “probability” in x is established with a constantly moving particle (or even photon). The eigenfunction of d/dx (or rather $-id/dx$) which exhibits some kind of spatial invariance is $\exp(ipx)$. This contains two different x probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. We noted that d/dx is associated with p due to an impulse hit at say an x point. Thus various $\exp(ipx)$ s with different weights should appear together in a physical problem with impulses such as reflection/refraction. The weights of the various $\exp(ip_1 x)$, $\exp(ip_2 x)$ etc become linked to probabilities associated with the state 1, 2 etc. Thus the origin of these probabilities (i.e. their specific values) follow from the probabilistic form $\exp(ipx)$ which follows from d/dx . (In (1) we have argued that the x distributions in $\exp(ipx)$ may be further linked to the force which “created” the p in the first place, with different p values having different distributions $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$).

Fermat’s Extremization of Time

The problem of reflection/refraction has been studied for a long time and is usually not thought of as a quantum mechanical or a statistical one. Fermat’s principle, applied separately in two dimensions to reflection and refraction, however, extremizes total time by writing it in terms of a free (invariant) spatial variable (x) which marks the changeable impulse point. For example, if a surface lies along the y axis at a fixed $x=0$, and light starts at $(x=0, Y)$ hits the surface at $(x, y=0)$ and moves to $(A-x, Y)$ in the case of reflection, one may vary x . Thus extremization of time really means applying d/dx , the generator of translation, in the direction of an invariant space variable linked to the impulse. This we argue is the main idea and points to quantum mechanics where d/dx is linked with the momentum operator. We argue that p and x are linked because an impulse (which creates p) occurs at a specific x point and if there is invariance in this variable then d/dx acting on a function yields p . One may generalize this to consider an eigenfunction of d/dx which is somewhat spatially invariant and yields p in that direction i.e.

$$-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((1)) \text{ where } p \text{ is momentum in the } x \text{ direction}$$

We have already discussed these ideas in previous notes. We have also noticed that the eigenfunction of $-i\hbar d/dx$, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$, has the statistical feature:

$$\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((2))$$

Here we wish to point out a different statistical feature which follows directly from the use of the generator $-i\hbar d/dx$, namely that the function on which it acts must contain x . From a classical point of view, no x should appear because a constant p value treats all x points as the same. We argue, however, that x is linked with impulses which may occur to p and so a constant p is still linked to x . In fact in (1) we argued that a given p was “created” through an impulse and still carries information about it. We argued that this occurs through the statistical distribution $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ of $\exp(ipx)$. As p changes, so do these, so they carry the “force” information of the various impulses because we argue that a force “maintains” the distribution $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$. Otherwise there would be no distribution in x .

As noted, we have discussed these ideas in previous notes, but here we wish to show that the probabilistic $\exp(ipx)$, based on the generator d/dx of an invariant variable, leads to “probabilities” in various physical problems. Here we focus on the one dimensional reflection/refraction problem.

One Dimensional Reflection/Refraction

We consider the problem of a photon moving in the positive x direction which strikes a surface along the y direction at $x=0$. There is a probability to reflect “ a ” and $1-a$ to refract. The question is: What are these probabilities? Traditionally (2), Maxwell’s electromagnetic equations are solved for a photon and the periodic electric field $E_0 \cos(-\omega t+kx)$ is applied to the problem in such a way that it and its first derivative are continuous at the impulse point. We suggest that the problem may be solved without knowing Maxwell’s equation or the solution for a photon.

The probabilities, however, must be based on some kind of physical idea (i.e something other than electric field continuity). We argue this idea is invariance. The impulse surface may be moved just as the x point in the two dimensional reflection or refraction problem using Fermat’s principle. Thus we suggest that again (and for consistency) d/dx should appear and yield p (the momentum in the x direction. This is the basis of the function $\exp(ipx)$ which is already statistical and ultimately governs the probabilities to reflect and refract. Thus there is a kind of double statistical nature to this problem, with one probability scheme controlling the other.

In the case of this one dimensional problem one does not simply have two rays as in the reflection only or refraction only Fermat’s extremization of time case. Here there are three rays which exist together, namely the incident A, the reflected B and the refracted C.

We point out an interesting feature related to time and space. For the Fermat’s reflection only or refraction only problem, the incident ray exists in a certain region of space and time, and the reflected or refracted ray in another with no overlap. In the one dimensional reflection and refraction problem, there are two different groupings. The time grouping is non-overlapping as

the incident photon exists in one time interval and the reflected or refracted photon in another. In terms of spatial grouping, however, the incident and reflected photon exist in the same region of space and the refracted in another overlapping one. The impulse point x separates the two. Given that we are interested in the translation operator d/dx linked to the impulse point x , we are interested in the spatial features of this problem and may ignore (or separate out) the time features. That does not mean that time features simply disappear. We will show that the spatial scheme gives rise to a consistent time one. The point we make is that the full analysis may be done in space with no time considerations.

We begin with the various $\exp(ipx)$ values in the problem namely $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(ip2x)$ for the incident, reflected and refracted light. These should have weights A, B, C , however, which will ultimately be linked to the probabilities to reflect or refract in terms of A , a weight for the incident beam (i.e. its strength). Thus $\exp(ipx)$ is the controlling probability in the problem. Using the notion of $-id/dx$ yielding a momentum type of equation, one should have two equations:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) \text{ (incident and reflected) and } C \exp(ip2x) \text{ (refracted) } \quad ((3))$$

Taking $-id/dx$ yields another equation:

$$Ap \exp(ipx) - Bp \exp(-ipx) \text{ and } Cp2 \exp(ip2x) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Equating at } x=0 \text{ yields: } A+B=C \text{ and } Ap - pB = p2C \quad ((5))$$

Combining yields a difference of squares result: $AAp - BBp = CCp2$ ((6)) which is equivalent to conservation of energy. In previous notes, we started with the conservation of energy equation ((6)) and created the two equations ((4)), ((5)) by using a difference of squares. This ensured energy conservation and provided the two equations needed for solving for the two unknowns B, C in terms of A .

We ask: How does one know that ((4)) and ((5)) are guaranteed to yield conservation of energy? We argue that the spatial grouping of the problem guarantees the difference of squares needed to ultimately create the energy conservation equation. This means that "B" (or ultimately BB) must be associated with a $-p$ which may then be brought to the RHS of the equation yielding a positive. The fact that A and B are grouped together in space in $A+B$ guarantees that the momentum associated with B must be negative. Thus when $-id/dx$ is applied, $A \rightarrow pA$ and $B \rightarrow -pB$. This automatically creates a difference of squares upon multiplication. Thus $AAp - BBp$ shows there are opposite momenta in space, but bringing $-BBp$ to the RHS converts the minus into a positive which may be associated with a positive energy at a different time.

Thus the energy conservation equation may be seen in two different ways:

$$AA/c1 = BB/c1 + CC/c2 \quad ((7a)) \text{ or } AAp - pBB = CCp2 \quad ((7b)) \text{ where } E=|p|c_i \text{ and } E \text{ is the same for all}$$

((7a)) shows separation in time while ((7b)) separation space. Thus, we argue that one thinks either in terms of time or in terms of space, but not the two at the same time. We argue this is consistent with $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$. In a two slit interference problem one considers $\exp(ipx)$ s and ignores $\exp(-iEt)$. The same idea holds for a quantum bound state i.e. the time-independent Schrodinger equation. We argue that this separation of time and space already occurs in the one dimensional reflection/refraction problem.

Nature of Statistics in the Problem

It is sometimes argued that probabilities exist because one does not know the full details of a mechanical problem. For example, a coin has two faces and one might argue that if one knew all of the parameters during a coin toss, one could predict with certainty whether a particular flip will be heads or tails. The idea of $\frac{1}{2}$ heads and $\frac{1}{2}$ tails means one does not know the details of a toss and assumes no bias on average.

In the reflection/refraction problem, there is a detailed interaction with the atoms/electrons of the medium, but we have argued that it is the idea of spatial invariance, leading to two spatial probabilities in $\exp(ipx)$, which ultimately governs of the probabilities of reflection/refraction. (It is not an equal .5,.5 based on the two possible outcomes.) The spatial invariance in turn is linked to the nature of the interaction i.e. an impulse at a certain x point.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in quantum mechanical problems (light, particles with rest mass) probability distributions, e.g. $\exp(ipx)$, exist in situations where classically one would not expect there to be any probability associated with x. This is linked to a generator (e.g. $-i\hbar d/dx$) which in turn is linked to invariance of a spatial variable linked to the force (impulse) at x. For example, p is created by an impulse which occurs at some x point. Thus p and x are intertwined even as the particle moves with constant p in space. It is this behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$ which governs “other” probabilities, such as the probability to reflect/refract in a one dimensional problem, because these probabilities are linked to the weights of various $\exp(ipx)$ s. Thus one probabilistic scheme controls the other.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Free Particle//Photon Energy, Information, Force and Spacetime (preprint, zenodo, 2023)
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change